

Personality Traits of Public Secondary School Principals in Urbiztondo, Division of Pangasinan

Arnold V. Austria Jr. ¹
1 – Palaris Colleges

Publication Date: May 9, 2026

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20096059](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20096059)

Abstract

This descriptive-normative study examined the personality traits of 337 teachers and 9 school administrators in public secondary schools across four districts of Urbiztondo, Pangasinan. The investigation focused on five key areas: contribution of personality traits to wholesome personality, factors affecting personality, encountered problems, need for personality improvement, and beliefs about physical characteristics. Results indicated that personality traits moderately contributed to wholesome personality (AWM=2.15). Intellectual factors (AWM=2.38) and creativity/critical thinking (AWM=2.39) showed much effect on personality development. Teachers encountered moderately serious problems including lack of self-control (AWM=1.86) and pretenses (AWM=1.85). A moderate need for personality improvement was identified (AWM=2.09). Physical characteristics played a moderate extent (AWM=1.73) on impressions made on others. ANOVA results revealed no significant differences among the four district groups across all variables, leading to acceptance of all null hypotheses at $\alpha=0.05$.

Keywords: *personality traits, school principals, wholesome personality, emotional intelligence, social competence, intellectual capacity, physical characteristics, teacher development, Pangasinan, educational management*

Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM

Rationale

When a person's behavior manifests successful adjustment to a given area of his environment, his personality in that area would be considered effective.

Achieving an all-around good personality depends upon developing satisfactory behavior patterns in many different aspects of living. A man with all the characteristically sound responses for success in business may be inept socially, since the responses for business and for such social success are not necessarily identical.

The key to a good personality is the ability to adjust equally well to various types of life situations to make those responses which result in the greatest satisfaction for both oneself and one's associates. The person who has learned to conduct himself positively in all the important areas of his life has developed an effective personality.

In any description of a person, the details, features, traits, and patterns of behavior that characterize him fall into certain broad spheres may be identified separately as physical, intellectual, emotional, and social. These four plus the person's overall value system constitute the spheres of personality. Let us briefly identify each sphere.

Posture, body build and size, complexion and facial expression as well as the appropriateness and condition of clothes, comprise the physical appearance of the person.

How the person talks, the range of ideas he expresses, and the things he talks about, as well as his values and mental alertness give evidence of his intellectual capacity.

A person's emotional make – up is shown by his likes and dislikes, whether he is aggressive or docile, how he responds when things become difficult, whether he is fully calm and self-reliant, how quickly he is given to anger, whether he can take a joke, what kind of a sense of humor he possesses and the like.

Another sphere of the personality deals with social qualities – how well the person conducts himself with other people and how well he observes the rules of etiquette that govern society. The value system is the person's attitudes toward life, his moral principles, his beliefs. Each person's philosophy of life and his values are the results of meaningful and satisfying learning experiences from which inner feelings and beliefs develop.

The five – fold classification, however, should not lead one to assume that personality can be divided into exact pieces like a pie. Although separate aspects of an individual's behavior are distinguishable it is his total behavior which is evaluated as his personality.

It is a common belief that the success or failure of the child in school largely depends on the teacher. The teacher plays a very crucial role in the teaching – learning process. As Strang and Morris, put it, guiding pupils in learning is the teacher's main responsibility. Successful learning by every pupil is the teacher's main goal.

Kolesniks, perception of the teacher's role is to help others acquire the knowledge and skills, the habits and attitudes, the ideals and aspirations with society deems necessary or valuable for its young members.

Our society needs teachers who can really teach who can "deliver the goods", and who can facilitate the attainment of desired learning outcomes.

What then are the characteristics of effective teachers? What must a teacher do or possess in order to success in his profession?

Even administrators who select and direct teachers do not always agree on the essential traits and distinguishing characteristics of a successful teacher. The reason for this difficulty in defining success in teaching stems from the complexity of the teacher's task.

However, many educators believe that although a teacher is concerned primarily with the intellectual development of her pupils, she is first of all a human being. As such, she could have a good understanding of the nature of the learner and the learning process.

Conceptual Framework

This study is founded on the concept that a school heads personality is vital in the teaching – learning situation. Thus, the personality traits that he exhibits in his job as he relates with learners, associates and superiors, make him what he is.

Personality as is often stated is the reflection or interpretation of one's inner self to other people. From this point of view, one is like an actor on a stage before an audience that will inevitably judge his performance.

Personality, then, is shown through a person's total behavior and by the responses of other people to that behavior. The impact of a person's behavior causes others to respond favorably or unfavorably. This process can also be reversed.

A person's concept of how he impresses others can be a strong force in modifying his behavior either to his advantage or disadvantage.

Achieving an all-around good personality depends upon developing satisfactory behavior patterns in many different aspects of living. A man with all the characteristicly, since the responses for business and for social success are not necessarily identical. The person who has learned to conduct himself positively in all the important areas of his life has developed an effective personality.

Operational Paradigm of the Study

The operational paradigm of this is composed of three variables namely: the independent variables, the dependent variables and the expected outcomes.

The independent variables are: personality traits of the school heads and teachers in

Urbiztondo Division of Pangasinan I factors affecting the personality traits of school heads in the public secondary schools in problems encountered by the teachers on their personality; personality traits of teachers that need to be improve in the four district of Urbiztondo; and teachers belief that physical characteristics play a part in the impression they make on others in Urbiztondo Division of Pangasinan I.

The dependent variables are: level of contribution and comparison among the perceptions of the teachers in 4 district of Urbiztondo on the level of contribution of personality traits to a wholesome personality, level of effect and comparison among the perceptions of the teachers in Urbiztondo Pangasinan I on the level of effect of the factors that affect the personality of school heads, teachers; degree of seriousness of problems encountered and comparison among the perceptions of the teachers in Urbiztondo Pangasinan I on the degree of seriousness of problems encountered on their personality; degree of need and comparison among the perceptions of the teachers in 4 districts of Urbiztondo Pangasinan on the degree of need to improve their personality; and, extent of belief and comparison among the perceptions of the teachers in 4 district of Urbiztondo, Pangasinan on the extent by which the teachers belief that physical characteristics play a part in the impression they make on other.

The expected outcomes are: improved personality of teachers in the 4 district of Urbiztondo Pangasinan, better results of the factors affecting the personality traits of teachers in Urbiztondo, Pangasinan; solutions to problems encountered relative to the personality traits of teachers in the 4 districts of San Carlos City; improvement on the personality traits of teachers; improved attitude towards the physical characteristics that play a part on the personality of teachers.

Conceptual Paradigm of the Study

Figure 1. Paradigm of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This study dealt with the personality traits of teachers in the public secondary schools in Urbiztondo Pangasinan, 2026 – 2027.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of contribution of personality traits of teachers and school heads to a wholesome personality?
 - 1.a Are there significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers in the public secondary schools of Urbiztondo, Pangasinan on the level of contribution of personality traits of teachers and school heads to a wholesome personality?
2. What is the level of effects of the factors that affect the personality of teachers and school heads?
 - 2.a Are there significant differences among the perceptions of teachers in public secondary school heads on the level of effect of the factors that affect the personality of teachers and school heads?
3. What are the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered by teachers and school heads relative to their personality?
 - 3.a Are there significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers and school heads of Urbiztondo Pangasinan on the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered by the teachers relative to their personality?
4. What is the degree of need to improve the personality of teachers in the public secondary schools in Urbiztondo, Pangasinan.
 - 4.a Are there significant differences among the perceptions of teachers and school head in secondary schools in Urbiztondo, Pangasinan.
5. To what extent do the teachers believe that physical characteristics play a part on the impressions they make on others?
 - 5.a Are there significant difference among the perceptions of the teachers and school heads in public secondary schools in Urbiztondo on the extent by which the teachers believe that physical characteristics play a part on the impression they make on others?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested in this study:

1. There are no significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers and school heads in public secondary schools in Urbiztondo, Pangasinan on the extent of contribution of personality traits of teachers to a wholesome personality.
2. There are no significant difference among the perceptions of the teachers and school heads in public secondary schools district of Pangasinan on the level of effect of the factors that affect the personality of teachers.
3. There are no significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers and school heads in public secondary school district of Urbiztondo on the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered by the teachers relative to their personality.
4. There are no significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers and school heads in public secondary schools in Urbiztondo Pangasinan on the degree of need to improve their personality.
5. There are no significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers and school heads

in public secondary schools of Urbiztondo, Pangasinan on the extent by which the teachers believe that physical characteristics play a part on the impression they make on others.

6.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study was delimited on the personality traits of teachers in the public secondary in Urbiztondo 2025 – 2026 which are as follows: contribution to a wholesome personality traits of teachers; factors affecting the personality traits of teachers; problems encountered on the personality traits of teachers; personality traits of teachers that need to be improved; and the teachers belief that physical characteristics play a part in the impression they make on others.

Importance of the Study

The teacher personality traits will bring about successful teaching, thus this writer is motivated to undertake this study. However, this is not only delimited to personality traits of teachers and school heads but also includes their level of performance. The writer would like to find out if teachers' personality traits are related with their performance. It is hoped that through the results of this study, the teachers may be further enlightened on the need for them to develop certain personality traits which could be revealed as wanting in them. Likewise, if a significant relationship will be noted between personality traits and performance, the teachers may be inspired continuously to keep on improving their personality traits.

The administrators may also profit from this study. By analyzing the results of the study, they could be guided on what specific aspect of personality traits their teachers need to improve on. This could be utilized as inputs for the administrators in planning a functional faculty development program which is responsive to the needs and problems of the teachers.

Definition of Terms Used

To have a clearer understanding of this study, the following terms used were operationally defined. They were lifted from the same reference.

Emotional Traits. These pertain to the power of man to express his feelings. As used in this study, some of the indicators of emotional traits of a teacher are: temperament, control of emotions, self-confidence, religious tolerance, racial attitudes, respect for human dignity, sensitiveness, etc.

Intellectual. These refer to the mental powers or faculties possessed by the teachers. Some indicators of intellectual traits as used in this study are: The degree of application of knowledge to school or job, ability to organize time efficiently, ability to express oneself orally, wide range and kind of reading materials, desire to acquire new knowledge.

Personality Traits. Klausmeier and Goodwin define this as the distinct and unique organization of traits in an individual as reflected in how he reacts to himself and others and in how they react to him, and also in how he meets frustrations and conflicts – that is, how he adjusts to his environment. As used in this study, personality traits of teachers are composed of four aspects, namely: physical, intellectual, social and emotional.

Physical Traits. These refer to the condition of the body as manifested by: posture, grooming, habits, selection of appropriate and becoming, clothing, sufficient sleep, proper food, and adequate exercise.

Pupil / Student Achievement. This is one of the aspects of performance of teachers which includes the extent in which the targeted objectives in terms of achievement of knowledge

and skills is realized.

Social Traits. These refers to the distinctive qualities of gregariousness or being friendly and enjoying the company of other people. As used in the study, some indicators of social traits are: courtesy and consideration of others, tact and diplomacy, recreational interest, sense of humor, zest for life, and ability to get along well with others.

Teacher Competence. This comprises the rating obtained by the teacher in terms of development of national consciousness and desirable values and beliefs, instructional materials, development, pupil evaluation, professional growth, records and report management, community and allied services, and punctuality and attendance. This comprises the rating obtained by the teacher in terms of development of national consciousness and desirable values and beliefs, instructional materials, development, pupil evaluation, professional growth, records and report management, community and allied services, and punctuality and attendance.

Teacher Performance. This refers to the efficiency of the teachers as a result of the performance evaluation for teachers which consider three aspects: pupil / student achievement, teacher's competence and teachers performance is categorized into five levels; Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fair and Unsatisfactory.

Teacher Personality and Human Relations. This aspect include the teachers' morality and integrity, personal characteristics, and human relations.

Personality Traits

More often relationship of teachers to their pupils or students is one of the factors which fosters success of teachers and learners. Teachers have varying attitudes. Authorities of education have endeavor to point-out ideal characteristics of teachers: In the classrooms and in dealing with the students, teachers must be careful not to permit small infraction to irritate them and grow into feelings of resentment and hostility. Hostile feelings build into lasting resentment and powerfully negative atmosphere will permeate the classroom if the irritating incidents that cause them are not dealt with as they occur.

Many times teachers explode emotionally in this situation. But positive students – teacher confrontation in which the teacher models, an attitude of respect can lead to open communication between the teachers and the student. James Kelly cited some qualities of a good teacher: 1) Alert in the classroom to expressions that communicate deep or strong feelings, and tries to understand these emotions from the student's points of view. 2) Aware that he or she has major influences on the emotional mood or climate of the classroom learning environment. 3) Allows for one to one contacts with individual students; these subtle but important contacts are exceptionally important for shy withdrawn students who are sometimes ignored; 4) Aware of self, 5) Models openness by sharing feelings and thoughts; 6) Recognizes their own limitations as well as their strengths, 7) Are continually seeking new or additional methods to facilitate learning in their classroom. 8) Actively listen to students when they talk, thus communicating a strong sense of caring, 9) Develops a teaching style that is genuine as described by noted psychologist, 10) Gives the students a feeling of being able to contribute to the school, community and society in general, 11) fosters a sense on the part of their students; awareness focuses on the here-and-how, helping the student become conscious of his or her total living self, as it relates to others and the environment. 12) Typically involves learners in planning; implementing and to some extent evaluating their own educational experiences.

Teaching as a profession has gained momentous appellation by almost everyone.

However, one cannot experience the real joy of a profession if he has not felt his effectiveness as teacher, and to be effective, he must know the qualities appealed by the majority of the people. Lardizabal defines effective teacher as the one who gets results. A class of college English when asked of the traits of characteristics of the effective teacher ranked results revealed the following: kindness and understanding, mastery of subject matter, patience, respect for the dignity and worth of the individual, consideration, pleasant personality, fairness no favoritism, emotional maturity, guidance oriented, effective communication, relaxed classroom atmosphere and sense of humor.

Factors that Affect a Teacher's Personality

A teacher's personality has an inculcable impact on her pupils. It is within a teacher's power to inspire her pupils, to encourage and challenge them to implant a sense of responsibility and perseverance, and to the development of their imagination, unfortunately the reverse may be true, teacher can have an undesirable effect or influence on her class. Although the perfect teacher does not exist, as the perfect human being does not exist. There are teachers who possess the qualities of excellence. Superior teachers have most of these qualities and average or artisan teachers. Here is a listing of these: Emotional stability and sound mental health. A teacher's sense of personal worth, security, and self-respect carries over in her attitude to her pupils. She recognizes individual personal worth, children to her are persons, not bothersome charges. She takes a sincere interest in people, treating them with respect, politeness and understanding. She is reliable and cooperative. This basic requirement of mental and emotional maturity encompasses other qualities as well as sociability, adaptability, reasonableness and a sense of humors. These by no means exhaust the number of qualities involved in this primary consideration.

Physical Health and Dynamic Personality

Teaching is an exhausting occupation and exact a toll in the nervous system. Good health is a good requisite. Children are enthusiastic about an alive teacher who though appearance and action demonstrates zest for life, passion of knowledge and spirit of adventure. Here ardous equals or exceeds that of her more spontaneous pupils, and she can awaken a reciprocal reaction in even the most lakadaisacal pupils.

Above Average Intelligence

To convey subject knowledge to her pupils, she must grasp and understand it completely. She must be always learning and desirous of furthering her own professional development. She must have ample knowledge of child development so that she knows how much to expect of her children. While some may argue that a teacher with a high IQ will not be patient with slower functioning, this can be a controverted ideas for impatient people may be found at all levels of intelligence.

Creativity, Imagination and Resourcefulness

The better teacher tries new method, invents new ways of illustrating ideas, tries several approaches when a child is confused over a problem, glance fresh materials for her lessons from likely and unlikely source, and uses ingenuity in gathering concrete materials to illustrate her lessons. She sets goals and has vision of what she hopes her pupils will accomplish while in her classroom and even in years.

Good Grooming, Imagination and Resourcefulness

A testful appearance accompanied by a grace of manner and pleasing voice can be important assets in the classrooms. This statement does not apply only to women: in a male teacher, cultured, well educated and well spoken would be applicable adjectives.

Courtesy, Kindness, Sympathy and Tact.

The courteous teacher reflects in her pupils who look to her as a model. Kindness and sympathy should go hand in hand in the compassionate teacher. A sympathetic world or kindly attention to a child's physical emotions, injury may be remembered by the child as expression of compassions and tenderness, and yield nothing but longed for a result.

Patience

Teachers should take note that human beings forget a very high proportions of what is learned and understood initially, and those with lesser abilities forget more and more rapidly, than do the gifted ones. Teacher must return patiently to a re-teaching situations and try not to register by word or gesture, disappointment or annoyance with result. She must also stretch her patience in the behavioral field, particularly with those children she tends to regard as nuisance or troublemakers in the classroom.

Sincerity and Honesty

Teachers have to be honest and truthfulness in their dealings with children because children quickly detect insincerity.

Fairness

Children admire a teacher who is firm with them, though the teacher must guard against firmness, hardening into rigidity. If she reverses her decision frequently, children wont know what to expect of her.

Positive and Encouraging Attitude.

To bring forth the best from her pupils, the good teacher praises them when they have made progresses, encourage them when they are discourage and urge them on to a greater effort when they haven't given an adequate response.

Professional Status

The responsible teacher accepts position of leadership with her profession, establishes friendly relation with her colleagues, and farther her own academic upgrading and professional development. The good teacher is herself a continuous learner in addition to being a knowledgeable – learned person.

Teaching is a joint venture of the teacher and parents. It is therefore necessary that a close linkage of parents and teachers be established. This linkage can not be held firm if teachers in the classrooms hesitate or failed to establish rapport to the parents of the children, because teachers in their capacity are surrogates of the mothers where the trust and confidence are built up for purposes of teaching. However, the teachers main concern is the maximum development of the child according to Castro hence all efforts are here directed toward the achievement of this goal. Since the child does not live alone, this development can be achieved only in relation with

other people. The teacher therefore, should seek to establish happy human relationship among the children at the same time that she works toward the achievement of the objectives of teaching.

The kind of human relationship which exists in the classroom will depend to a large extent upon the teachers attitude toward her pupils. In helping them to meet their basic needs, to improve their social adjustment and to achieve their acceptability in the group, the teachers should establish and maintain mutual respect for the friendly contact with each of them.

Another trait imperative for a school teacher in the Philippine Educational System is the ability of the teacher to win the sympathy of the people in the community. The school teachers in the country are very important agents of public relations, because they have intimate contacts with the children and their parents. However, apparently very little has been done by school administrators to make the teachers effective in this respect. I can also be said that the teachers have recognized responsibilities in the field of public relations as an indispensable assets to a school and should therefore be concerned with policies that tend to develop them.

Since teachers are agents of promoting school community relationship, they must be imbued with traits and characteristics which end to bring people in the community closer to each other, however, this trait of teachers are not inborn, but acquired through education and long experience of teaching. Timid teachers bring gap of relationship. If the teacher is to become the moving force in the community education, the education of the teacher assumes added importance. The program of teacher-training institution must be based upon a broad point of view which result in large scale social, political and economic planning.

Problems Encountered by Teachers Relative to their Personality

Aquino in his long years of academic studies and as an experienced educational authority also prescribed some undesirable characteristics of teachers: sarcastic, grouchy, given to ridicule, lacks animation, give the appearance of or is lazy, superiority complex, overbearing, haughty, arrogant, inferiority complex, insecure, defensive, hangdog, narrow outlook and interests, Impatience, inconsiderate, tactless, avarice that is weak, shrill, harsh, monotonous or strident. Ill-mannered, unsympathetic, discourteous, harsh, or overly strict. Deceitful, dishonest, insincere. Too changeable, vascillating, unreliable, inconsistent, not prompt, unable to keep to a schedule. Slovenly in appearance, grooming in bad taste, unfriendly, and unsociable, unsystematic and disorganized. Dull, uninteresting. Emotionally unstable, unreasonable. Inadaptable, disrespectful on the opinions of others. Laughs at rather than witty to some of her pupils. Lacks imagination, not resourceful or ingenuity.

Traits such as these are to be avoided. There are other indications of the poor teacher. Some in the form of lead habits or distracting actions. An uninspiring, poor teacher is inclined to:

Play with chalk or some other object, lean on the furniture; pace restlessly back and forth; Snap her fingers or tap the desk to attract attention; Speak indistinctly, fail to motivate her class; Bring into her lesson or activities irrelevant materials; Use only the example given in the text book or use inappropriate examples; Fail to provide for individuals differences or make little provisions for them; Fail to give individuals assistance and attentions; Never depart from the organization of the materials as is presented in the textbook; Use very fee teaching aids; Never take her class on fieldtrips and excursions; Give mostly page to page assignment; Not very clear methods or the appearance from lesson to lesson; Ask factual question almost exclusively or use questions above the pupils head; Decline to answer pupils questions or give unsatisfactory answers; Give out misinformation; Repeat pupils answers without adding anything of value;

Permit her desk and the room in general to be untidy or in state of disorder; Tolerate inattention, whispering and interruption, or demand the equally undesirable and opposite state of absolute silence with pupils with tiptoeing about the room; Text her pupils infrequently, usually only at a formal examination time. Fail to return children's work or never mark it all; Avoid newer type of examination. Threaten punishment often and admonish or tirade of abuse infrequently and stall for time and repeat what she has said before.

All teachers perform public relation function at sometime or other and probably oftener than they are aware. In serving in a public relation function, teachers help the public to arrive at a better understanding of what schools do and what they are trying to accomplish. Schools administrators are of course, the chief public relation representatives, because they have direct access to the community through the News Media and through their contacts with the board of education. Official pronouncements also come from administrators rather than from individual teachers. Thus the interaction between teachers and parents provides the major opportunity for teachers to play public relation roles. Contacts are during the occasional home visits, at parents-teacher meetings, and during parental visits to the school. Almost three fourths of the teachers said that they spent sometimes with parents. The involvement with parents is one of the characteristics that make the school unique. In other countries, parents are expected to stay away from school.

Powell revealed that communication frequency is positively related to pre-school rule function, friendship, relation with parents, and attitudes that child rearing values should be discussed with parents. It was further found out when measure adapted to test it that there was relationship between the years of experience of training of teachers and formal training; that there was relationship found out over the said variables. It was further found out that age, years of formal education, and amount of special training were not statistically significant predicates of teachers communication frequency or diversity, even though years of formal education is positively correlated with both of these communicative behavior dimensions.

In another finding, there is no significant relationship between most of the predictive variables and communication frequency and diversity. Communication behavior is moderately correlated with parents friendship and relationship with other parents and more strongly corresponds to family information and child rearing values.

The above – study has its close relevance to this research since it is one of the purpose of this writings to find out how far the relationship established by the children's parents, such that the success is determined by the support of the parents and his people in the community.

While it is true that education starts at home, the school where teachers are properly trained for the total upbringing of their pupils or students plays a vital role in the educative process. Parents, students, and the public relied much on the ability of teachers, especially on the psychological, social intellectual, and emotional needs of individuals. For this reason, teachers have more chances over their students, particularly in the teaching – learning process.

“Loving teachers produce affectionate students”, says Divina. The act of love is more important than education, clothing, food and shelter. With much love, care, and encouragement, pupils or students will become good and successful about which teachers will be proud of love, assurance, sense of security and recognition, and a feeling of belongingness will provide a deep bed of affection and trust which will make student respond sensitively to one's teaching or training although they are not supervised.

Love is the fulfillment of the law; if you love someone, you will never do his wrong. The teacher's relationship with his students manifests love, understanding, peace, feeling, and wants of student as individuals to develop good habits, attitudes, skills and values.

There is no greater opportunity to influence the way a child will turn out then by the example his teachers met.

The teachers who brag about how he cheated the government, or how he manipulated things to influence the approval of his superior, will never expect his pupils to be honest, God-fearing, and law-abiding citizens.

A teacher cannot discipline his student if he cannot discipline himself. His everyday dealing with pupils, teachers, parents, and fellow workers will reveal his innate characteristics and behavior. The exercise of his power and authority, a sincere dedication to his duties and functions coupled with a find appreciation of the beautiful and just contribute to the influence of good discipline among students.

Accept the responsibility of leading the youth. Being the second parents of children in school, teachers should accept the responsibility of leading and guiding the students by developing their moral and spiritual values, mental and physical health, economic well-being, and human and public relations as well. It is also their concern to love, discipline, teacher, and be a living model to their students.

Training involves the development of character. It also includes respect for elders and one's property. Teaching and training requires patience, time and repetition until students have developed their good habits and attitudes, skills, and understanding, interest and abilities and an application of the moral and spiritual values in life. The teacher should see to it that standard norms of conduct are properly developed and applied to minimize the social ills of the school and society.

Physical Characteristics Play a Part on the Impression They Make on Others

As a means of prediction, palmistry, the belief that lives on one's hand tell the fate and destiny of an individual still has a place among us. It is also believed that the form and shape of one's hand reveal personality traits or types. Even the shape of the fingernails is believed to indicate certain physical handicaps.

Still another technique of character – analysis is phrenology, whereby an individual's traits, such as honesty, sympathy, love, mathematical ability, or musical talent can be determined by the size and shape of the head, the form of the forehead, and so on.

Physiognomy, which is allied to phrenology, predicts personality traits through facial characteristics bodily structure, or muscular set, like the size of the head, nose, eyes, ears, chin, or the texture of skin and hair. We hear of a stern mouth or cold blue eyes, but more often than not, continued association with persons has made us change our first impressions of them. The only overt signs of facial characteristics are lines on one's face, set lips and jaws when one is worried, and relaxed facial muscles when one is happy or contented. Scientists believe that there is little relationship between personality traits and physical characteristics.

Related Studies

Similar to the present study is that of Oducando. It attempted to obtain a comprehensive view of the different personality characteristics and attitudes of elementary and high school teachers of Immaculate Concepcion Academy of Manila and the type of relationships that exist

between certain personality traits and teachers efficiency rating. The data obtained from the two groups of teachers were analyzed using multiple correlation and regression analysis. The total group yielded a normal average mean in personality traits, above average score in orderliness, empathy, social conformity, emotional stability, extraversion, trust and activity.

Serrabia gave the following conclusions based on his findings on the personality traits and characteristics of elementary grades teachers in the Division of Pagadian City and Zamboanga del Sur: 1) Respondents manifest the same level of traits and characteristics relative to classroom management, community extension work and in pre-serving professional dignity even when grouped according to sex, age and educational qualifications; 2) the findings reveal that male and female teachers differ in their classroom management; 3) with regard to traits and characteristics of teachers relative to classroom management and age, it was found out that the two variances differ from each other, hence, ages of persons will bring variation in terms of management; 4) There was a significant difference in traits and characteristics of teachers relative to classroom management and educational qualifications. The higher the education attained by the respondents, the greater manifestation of change he will have; 5) With regard to respondents' community extension service and sex, there was a significant difference in their traits and characteristics relative to community extension work and sex. However, the difference in seen only in their way of leading people; 6) As regard difference in traits and characteristics of respondents relative to community extension work and age, there was found a significant difference in these variables. Therefore ages bring changes in the perspective of teachers relative in their community extension services; 7) The findings reveals that there was a significant difference in traits and characteristics of teachers toward their community extension work when grouped according to their educational qualifications. Therefore, the higher the education, the greater interest of service to the community will the teacher have while in the service of teaching; 8) It was also seen that there was a significant difference in traits and characteristics of teachers relative to preserving professional dignity and sex. Respondents of different sexes therefore have different ways of preserving their professional dignity; and 9) Qualifications, such as education, experience and other trainings will bring new perspectives of the respondents ways of preserving professional dignity. This was also the findings with regards to ages. Ages also bring variation of perspective in manner of preserving professional dignity.

Chapter 2

Research Methodology

This chapter presents the research design, locale and population of the study, data gathering tool and statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study is basically descriptive-normative in design. It was descriptive since it described to some extent the personality traits of teachers; factors affecting the personality of teachers; problems encountered by the teachers relative to their personality; personality traits that need to be improved and the teachers' belief that physical characteristics play a part in the impressions they make on others.

It was normative in design since it statistically treated the data gathered based on norms.

Locale and Population of the Study

This study was conducted in Public Secondary Schools in Urbiztondo, Pangasinan. 337 teachers and 9 school administrators were taken as respondents from each school thereby coming up with an aggregate of teachers-respondents from whose perceptions the data in this study were taken.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondent

Table 1

Distribution of Subject Respondent by School (JHS)

School	Number of School Heads	Number of Teachers
1. Urbiztondo National High School	1	52
2. Balangay National High School	1	40
3. Galarin National High School	1	45
4. Real National High School	1	42
5. Bayaoas Integrated School	1	38
6. Urbiztondo Integrated School	1	36
7. Dalanguiring Integrated School	1	28
8. Urbiztondo Private School	1	27
9. Urbiztondo Catholic School	1	29
Total	9	337

Data Gathering Tool

The questionnaire was the main data gathering tool used in this study. This was constructed before the proposal of this study and it was defended with the operational paradigm and the statement of the problems.

After the proposal defense, it was shown to the adviser who suggested some improvements before it was reconstructed to its final form.

Validation of the Questionnaire

The questionnaire was pre-tested to 16 classmates of the researcher in the Graduate school. This was to find out if they could have some suggestions as to the improvement of its content, organization and mechanics. The pre-test questionnaire were retrieved and examined. Since there were no suggestions, the researcher concluded that it could be fit for floating.

The researcher floated the questionnaire after requesting permission from the Schools' Superintendent. She was assisted by school heads, teachers, friends and relative in its floating and retrieval.

Statistical Treatment

The researcher tallied and tabulated the data gathered. Then she asked the assistance of her adviser how to obtained the weighted mean and the general average weighted mean per district. After that he was introduced to the computation of the F using the ANOVA (Analysis of variance).

The following procedure shows how the statistical treatment was conducted:

1. The level of contribution of the personality traits of teachers was measured with the following relative values:

- 3 - Much Contributed (MC)
- 2 - Moderately Contributed (MOC)
- 1 - Least Contributed (LC)

The computed means for this particular analysis were as follows:

- 2.34 – 3.00 Much Contributed (MC)
- 1.67 – 2.33 Moderately Contributed (MOC)
- 1.00 – 1.66 Least Contributed (LC)

2. The level of effect of the factors that affect the personality of teachers was measured with the following relative value:

- 3 - Much Effect (ME)
- 2 - Moderate Effect (MOE)

1 - Least Effect (LE)

The computed means for this particular analysis were as follows:

2.34 – 3.00 Much Effect (ME)

1.64 – 2.33 Moderate Effect (MOE)

1.00 – 1.66 Least Effect (LE)

3. The degree of seriousness of the problems encountered by teachers relative to their personality was measured with the following relative values:

3 - Very Serious (VS)

2 - Moderately Serious (MS)

1 - Least Serious (LS)

The computed means for this particular analysis were as follows:

2.34 – 3.00 Very Serious (VS)

1.67 – 2.33 Moderately Serious (MS)

1.00 – 1.66 Least Serious (LS)

4. The degree of need to improve the personality of teachers was measured with the following relative values:

3 - Much Needed (MN)

2 - Moderately Needed (MON)

1 - Least Needed (LN)

The computed means for this particular analysis were as follows:

2.34 – 3.00 Much Needed (MN)

1.67 – 2.33 Moderately Needed (MON)

1.00 – 1.66 Least Needed (LN)

5. The extent by which the teachers believe that physical characteristics play a part on the impressions they make on others was measured with the following relative values:

3 - Great Extent (GE)

2 - Moderate Extent (MOE)

1 - Least Extent (LE)

The computed means for this particular analysis were as follows:

2.33 – 3.00 Great Extent (GE)

1.67 – 2.33 Moderate Extent (MOE)

1.00 – 1.66 Least Extent (LE)

The null hypotheses were tested by the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), F-test. The formula used was:

1. Determine the total sum-of-squares by finding the mean of the scores. Taking the deviation of each score from each mean, and squaring and summing these squared deviation.

The sum of the squares can be obtained by the used of the following equation:

$$SS_t = E_w^2 - \frac{E^2}{n}$$

2. Determine the between sum-of-squares by taking the mean of each group, getting its deviation from the total mean, squaring this deviation and then multiplying each of these by the number of individuals in each group (N), as follows:

$$SS_b = E (X - X_t)^2 n$$

3. The within sum-of-squares can be obtained by finding the sum-of-squares of each group as follows:

$$SS_w = E_t^2 - \frac{(E_w)^2}{n}$$

4. The within sum-of-squares added to the between sum-of-squares should total the total sum-of-squares can be obtained directly by subtracting the between sum-of-squares from the total sum-of-squares?

$$SS_w = SS_t - SS_b$$

The analysis of variance table is evaluated by making the following F test:

$$F = \frac{\text{Mean-Square for Between Group}}{\text{Mean-Square for Within Group}}$$

Chapter 3

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents, analysis and interprets the data gathered from the questionnaire. The salient features of the study directs the reader on: the personality traits of teachers; factors affecting the personality of teachers; problems encountered by the teachers relative to their personality; personality traits of teachers that need to be improved and the teachers' belief that physical characteristics play a part in the impressions they make on others.

The study was guided by the following null hypotheses:

1. There is no significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers in four districts of San Carlos City on the level of contribution of personality traits of teachers to a wholesome personality.
2. There is no significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers in four districts of San Carlos City on the level of effect of the factors that affect the personality of teachers.
3. There is no significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers in four district of San Carlos City on the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered by the teachers on their personality.
4. There is no significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers in the degree of need to improve their personality.
5. There is no significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers in San Carlos City on the extent by which the teachers believe that physical characteristics play a part on the impression they make on others.

Level of Contributions of Personality Traits to a Wholesome Personality

There were 8 personality traits that contribute to a wholesome personality that the teachers in Public Secondary School in Urbiztondo perceived on. They were the following: full of initiative; eloquent speaker; idealistic; emotional passionate; high intelligence; bright / alert; generous and thrifty.

Table 1 presents the level of contribution of the personality traits of teachers to a wholesome personality as perceived by the teachers.

The average weighted mean of 2.15 shows that the personality traits of teachers moderately contribute to a wholesome personality.

Table 1

Level of Contribution of the Personality Traits of Teachers to Wholesome Personality as Perceived by the Teachers

Personality Traits	WM	DE
1. Full of initiative	2.39	MC
2. Eloquent speaker	1.97	MOC
3. Idealistic	2.21	MOC
4. Emotional, passionate	2.11	MOC
5. High intelligence	2.16	MOC
6. Bright / alert	2.19	MOC
7. Generous	3.28	MC
8. Thrifty	1.89	MOC
TOTAL	17.2	
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	2.15	MOC

LEGEND:

MC	=	Much Contributed	2.34 – 3.00
MOC	=	Moderately Contributed	1.67 – 2.33
LC	=	Least Contributed	1.00 – 1.66
WM	=	Weighted Mean	
DE	=	Descriptive Equivalent	

On the 8 personality traits only one was perceived to have much contributed to a wholesome personality while 7 were perceived to have moderately contributed. They are arranged sequentially and presented as follows: full initiative ($x=2.39$); generous ($x=2.28$); idealistic ($x=2.21$); bright / alert ($x=2.19$); high intelligence ($x=2.16$); emotional/passionate ($x=2.11$); eloquent speaker ($x=1.97$); and thrifty ($x=1.89$).

The teachers in place much value on initiative as one personality traits that contribute to a wholesome personality of a teacher. It is because a teacher should possess that inner drive to do things without prodding. As a teacher, this individual who has the initiative can plan so many activities for the learners and so she is admired by her class. As a co-teacher, she can do so many things for her co-teachers, thus, she is desirable to her peers. To her administrators, she is always spoken of dearly. To the community, she is endeared.

Moreover, the teachers considered generosity as a personality trait that contributes to a wholesome personality.

It is because a teacher should not only be generous with material resources. She needs the material resources herself. However, she can be generous with her services if she can spare a little of her congested time schedule to be of service to others.

Table 1.1 presents the level of contribution of the personality traits of teachers to a wholesome personality as perceived by the teachers themselves.

The average weighted mean of 2.13 shows that the teachers perceived that the personality traits of teachers moderately contributed to a wholesome personality.

The teachers perceived that all the items moderately contributed to a wholesome personality. They are sequenced and presented as follows: full of initiative ($x=2.33$); idealistic ($x=2.27$); generous ($x=2.21$); bright / alert ($x=2.17$); high intelligence ($x=2.17$); emotional passionate ($x=2.03$); thrifty ($x=1.95$); and, eloquent speaker ($x=1.93$).

The teachers considered full of initiative as their first priority among the personality traits that contribute to a wholesome personality. It is truly a trait that overshadows other traits among teachers. Teachers are expected to possess this traits.

The teachers looked up at idealism as a second priority. It is a trait whereby a teacher should possess that strong desire to acquire what is desirable; to reach what dwells in the mind. It is because when one has an ideal, one works hard at it.

Table 1.1

Level of Contribution of the Personality Traits of Teachers to Wholesome Personality as Perceived by the teacher

Personality Traits	WM	DE
1. Full of initiative	2.33	MOC
2. Eloquent speaker	1.93	MOC
3. Idealistic	2.27	MOC
4. Emotional, passionate	2.03	MOC
5. High intelligence	2.17	MOC
6. Bright / alert	2.17	MOC
7. Generous		
8. Thrifty	1.93	MOC
TOTAL	17.04	
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	2.13	MOC

LEGEND:

MC	=	Much Contributed	2.34 – 3.00
MOC	=	Moderately Contributed	1.67 – 2.33
LC	=	Least Contributed	1.00 – 1.66
WM	=	Weighted Mean	
DE	=	Descriptive Equivalent	

Two items emerged as third in the priorities of the teachers. A bright/alert teacher is preferred from one who has little of it. This goes together with a generous teacher.

A bright/alert teacher brings sunshine to people she deals with. Her being bright/alert infects others and so she is much in demand in groups.

Table 1.2 presents the level of contribution of the personality traits of teachers to a wholesome personality as perceived by the teachers of District III.

The average weighted mean of 2.13 shows that the personality traits of teachers moderately contributed to a wholesome personality.

All the items were perceived to have moderately contributed to a wholesome personality. They are sequenced and presented as follows: full of initiative ($x=2.24$); bright/alert ($x=2.23$); eloquent speaker ($x=2.19$); thrifty ($x=2.17$); high intelligence ($x=2.12$); idealistic ($x=2.11$); emotional passionate ($x=2.10$); and generous ($x=1.9$).

Table 1.2

Level of Contribution of the Personality Traits of Teachers to Wholesome Personality as Perceived by the Teachers in District III

Personality Traits	WM	DE
1. Full of initiative	2.24	MOC
2. Eloquent speaker	2.19	MOC
3. Idealistic	2.11	MOC
4. Emotional, passionate	2.10	MOC
5. High intelligence	2.12	MOC
6. Bright / alert	2.23	MOC
7. Generous	1.9	MOC
8. Thrifty	2.17	MOC
TOTAL	17.06	
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	2.13	MOC

LEGEND:

MC	=	Much Contributed	2.34 – 3.00
MOC	=	Moderately Contributed	1.67 – 2.33
LC	=	Least Contributed	1.00 – 1.66
WM	=	Weighted Mean	
DE	=	Descriptive Equivalent	

The teachers considered that a teacher should be full of initiative. This was their foremost perception. She is expected to be full of initiative in her subject field in her class; in the midst of community development and among parents. The teacher is never short of initiative wherever she is and with whoever she associates. She cannot and should not deny people's expectations. Initiative makes the teacher the centerpiece of community activities. With initiative, she can assert herself to best advantage.

In the same manner, the bright/alert teacher is in demand. The vivacity of the bright/alert teacher makes her the star of her party. She is everyone's friend since everyone demands her company among all ages.

The teacher is considered generosity as the last traits of a teacher that contributes to a wholesome personality. It is because one cannot share what one does not have especially in terms of material resources. Teachers can be generous with their services but teachers are under time constraints no matter how they budget their time.

Table 1.3 presents the level of contribution of the personality traits of teachers to a wholesome personality as perceived by the teachers.

Table 1.3

Level of Contribution of the Personality Traits of Teachers to Wholesome Personality as Perceived by the Teachers in District IV

Personality Traits	WM	DE
1. Full of initiative	2.19	MOC
2. Eloquent speaker	2.14	MOC
3. Idealistic	2.16	MOC
4. Emotional, passionate	2.13	MOC
5. High intelligence	2.13	MOC
6. Bright / alert	2.19	MOC
7. Generous	1.96	MOC
8. Thrifty	2.44	MC
TOTAL	17.34	
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	2.17	MOC

LEGEND:

MC	=	Much Contributed	2.34 – 3.00
MOC	=	Moderately Contributed	1.67 – 2.33
LC	=	Least Contributed	1.00 – 1.66
WM	=	Weighted Mean	
DE	=	Descriptive Equivalent	

The total average weighted mean of 2.17 shows that the personality traits of teachers moderate contributed to a wholesome personality.

Of the 8 personality traits only one was perceived to have contributed much to a wholesome personality while all the others were perceived to have moderate contributed to a wholesome personality. They were sequenced and are presented as follows: thrifty ($x=2.44$); full of initiative ($x=2.19$); bright/alert ($x=2.19$); idealistic ($x=2.16$) eloquent speaker ($x=2.14$); emotional passionate ($x=2.13$); high intelligence ($x=2.13$); and generous ($x=1.96$).

The teachers considered thrift as the foremost trait that contributes to a wholesome personality. This implied that the teachers receive salaries that could not meet the needs of the family if they are not thrifty. Moreover, a teacher who is extravagant would be indebted to friends, neighbors, etc. this situation creates enemies among friends, neighbors, etc. this make unwholesome personality of teachers.

The teachers' second priority were "full of initiative" and "bright/alert" traits. This implied that the two traits have very close relationship. A teacher who is full of initiative is one who is bright/alert. She is an active teacher who is eager to accomplish tasks efficiently and effectively.

High intelligence did not appear as a first priority nor a last priority. It means that the teachers do not necessarily need to have high intelligence in order to possess a wholesome personality. The other traits outweigh high intelligence in order to possess a wholesome personality. The other traits outweigh high intelligence as a contributory trait to a wholesome personality.

The findings further implied that an emotional/passionate teacher was not much admired by the teacher-respondents of District IV. It meant that the teacher was not required to be too showy with her feelings. Stoicism is admired by some people as a trait that shows strengths of character. Showing one's feelings described as emotional / passionate betrays a weak personality.

Table 1.4 presents the comparison of the persons of the teachers in Urbizondo, Division of Pangasinan I on the level of contribution of the personality traits of teachers to a wholesome personality.

The combined perceptions of 2.15 shows the 4 groups of teachers perceived that the personality traits of teacher moderately contributed to a wholesome personality.

Table 1.4

Comparison of the Perceived Level of Contribution of the Personality Traits of Teachers to Wholesome Personality

Personality Traits	WM	DE
1. Full of initiative	2.29	MOC
2. Eloquent speaker	2.06	MOC
3. Idealistic	2.19	MOC
4. Emotional, passionate	2.09	MOC
5. High intelligence	2.14	MOC
6. Bright / alert	2.19	MOC
7. Generous	2.09	MOC
8. Thrifty	2.11	MC
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	2.15	MOC

F = 0.12 F_{0.05} = 2.95 df = 3/28

Result : No significant difference

Decision : Accept H₀

LEGEND:

MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00

MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33

LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66

WM = Weighted Mean

DE = Descriptive Equivalent

The combined perceptions in all the items show that the 4 groups of teachers perceived that the personality traits of teachers all moderately contributed to a wholesome personality. They are sequenced and presented as follows: full of initiative (x=2.29); idealistic (x=2.19); bright/alert (x=3.19); high intelligence (x=2.14); thrifty (x=2.11); emotional/passionate (x=2.09); generous (x=2.09); and eloquent speaker (x=2.06).

The ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) was used to determine significant difference of perceptions among the four groups of respondents.

In the testing, the Computed t-value of 0.12 was lower than the tabular F-value of 2.95 at 5 percent level of significance with 3/18 degrees of freedom. It shows that there was no significant difference among the perceptions of the 4 groups of teachers. Thus, the null hypothesis that states: There is no significant difference among perceptions of the teachers on the level of contribution of the personality traits of teachers to a wholesome personality, is accepted. It means that their perceptions were similar.

The findings concur with what Kelly cited as some qualities of a good teacher: 1) Alert in the classroom to expressions that communicate deep or strong feeling, and tries to understand these emotions from the student's point of view; 2) Aware that he or she has major influences on the emotional mood or climate of the classroom learning environment, among others.

Level of Effects of the Factors that Affect the Personality of Teachers

The teachers of Urbiztondo perceived on the level of effects of the factors that affect the personality of teachers. These factors were: A. Physical factors – 1) physical fitness, 2) cleanliness, 3) beauty, 4) art; B. Intellectual factors – 1) knowledge/truth, 2) creativity/critical thinking; C. Emotional factors – 1) integrity/honesty, 2) personal discipline, 3) self-worth/self-esteem; D. Social factors – 1) social responsibilities, 2) mutual love/respect, 3) fidelity, 4) responsible parenthood.

Table 2 presents the level of effect of the factors that affect the personality of teachers as perceived by the teachers.

The average weighted mean of 2.28 shows that the factors moderately affect the personality of teachers.

Taking the factors by subtopics, A. along physical factors, the responses were sequenced and presented as follows: (x=2.39) or much effect; cleanliness (x=2.39) or much effect; beauty (x=2.12) or moderate effect; art (x=2.00) or moderate effect.

B. Along intellectual factors, both were perceived to have much effect on the personality of teachers. They were knowledge / truth (x=2.38) and creativity / critical thinking (x=2.39).

C. Along emotional factors, integrity/honesty was perceived to have much effect (x=2.41) on the teacher's personality; personal discipline (x=2.3) and self-worth/self-esteem (x=2.19).

D. Along social factors, one item was perceived to have much effect and that was mutual love and respect (x=2.34). The other three were perceived to have moderate effect. They were: social responsibilities (x=3.00); responsible parenthood (x=2.23) and fidelity (x=2.17).

Table 2

Level of Effects of the Factors that Affect the Personality of Teachers as Perceived by the Teachers

Factors	WM	DE
1. Physical Factor		
a. Physical fitness	2.39	ME
b. Cleanliness	2.39	ME
c. Beauty	2.12	MOE
d. Art	2.0	MOE
2. Intellectual Factors		
a. Knowledge / truth	2.38	ME
b. Creative and critical thinking	2.39	ME
3. Emotional Factor		
a. Integrity / honesty	2.41	ME
b. Personal discipline	2.3	MOE
c. Self worth / self esteem	2.19	MOE
4. Social Factor		
a. Social responsibilities	2.3	MOE
b. Mutual love / respect	2.34	ME
c. Fidelity	2.17	MOE
d. Responsible parenthood	2.23	MOE
Total	29.61	
Average Weighted Mean	2.28	MOE

LEGEND:

MC	=	Much Contributed	2.34 – 3.00
MOC	=	Moderately Contributed	1.67 – 2.33
LC	=	Least Contributed	1.00 – 1.66
WM	=	Weighted Mean	
DE	=	Descriptive Equivalent	

The findings implied that the intellectual factors have much effect on the teachers personality and that teachers should develop these. The people that teachers associate with everyday most especially their pupils can easily detect the intellectual ability of their teacher. The teacher that betrays such traits affects the impression that the pupils have on him/her. The young learners are very good judges and they go out to the community and speak proudly about their intelligent teachers. That is because their teacher has a vast knowledge balanced with creativity.

Table 2.1 presents the level of effect of the factors that affect the personality of teachers as perceived by the teachers.

A. Along physical factors, physical fitness was perceived to have much effect ($x=2.38$) on the personality of teachers. The other three were perceived to have moderate effect. They were: cleanliness ($X=2.33$) beauty ($X=2.13$) and art ($X=1.97$).

B. Along intellectual factor, both items were perceived to have much effect on the personality of teachers. They were creative/critical thinking ($X=2.41$) and knowledge/truth ($X=2.6$).

Table 2.1

Level of Effect of the Factors that Affect the Personality of Teachers as Perceived by the Teachers

Factors	WM	DE
1. Physical Factor		
a. Physical fitness	2.38	ME
b. Cleanliness	2.33	MOE
c. Beauty	2.13	MOE
d. Art	1.97	MOE
2. Intellectual Factors		
a. Knowledge / truth	2.36	ME
b. Creative and critical thinking	2.41	ME
3. Emotional Factor		
a. Integrity / honesty	2.33	MOE
b. Personal discipline	2.26	MOE
c. Self worth / self esteem	2.15	MOE
4. Social Factor		
a. Social responsibilities	2.29	MOE
b. Mutual love / respect	2.27	MOE
c. Fidelity	2.12	MOE
d. Responsible parenthood	2.15	MOE
Total	29.15	
Average Weighted Mean	2.24	MOE

LEGEND:

MC	=	Much Contributed	2.34 – 3.00
MOC	=	Moderately Contributed	1.67 – 2.33
LC	=	Least Contributed	1.00 – 1.66
WM	=	Weighted Mean	
DE	=	Descriptive Equivalent	

C. Along emotional factor, all 3 items were perceived to have moderate effect. They were: integrity / honesty ($X=2.33$); personal discipline ($X=2.26$) and self-worth / self-esteem ($X=2.15$).

D. Along social factor, all four items were perceived to have moderate effect. They were: social responsibilities ($X=2.29$); mutual love/respect ($X=2.27$); responsible parenthood ($X=2.15$) and fidelity ($X=2.12$).

The average weighted mean of 2.24 shows that the teachers in District II perceived that the factors had a moderate effect on the personality of teachers.

Moreover, the findings implied that the teachers in District considered the intellectual factors to have much effect on the personality of teachers. It was because teachers are expected to possess intellectual abilities. The findings further implied that physical fitness should accompany intellectual abilities. Therefore, a teacher should possess a sound mind in a sound body in order to survive the rigors of a teacher's job.

Table 2.2 presents the level of effect of the factors that affect the personality of teachers as perceived by the teachers.

A. Along physical factors, the teachers perceived that physical fitness had much effect on the teacher's personality ($X=2.35$) and so with art ($X=2.37$). The other two were perceived to have moderate effect. They were: beauty ($X=2.04$) and cleanliness ($X=1.92$).

B. Along intellectual factors, the teachers perceived that creativity / critical thinking had much effect ($X=2.39$) while knowledge / truth had a moderate effect ($X=2.33$).

Table 2.2

Level of Effects of the Factors that Affect the Personality of Teachers as Perceived by the Teachers in District III

Factors	WM	DE
1. Physical Factor		
a. Physical fitness	2.35	ME
b. Cleanliness	1.92	MOE
c. Beauty	2.04	MOE
d. Art	2.37	ME
2. Intellectual Factors		
a. Knowledge / truth	2.33	MOE
b. Creative and critical thinking	2.39	ME
3. Emotional Factor		
a. Integrity / honesty	2.11	MOE
b. Personal discipline	2.29	MOE
c. Self worth / self esteem	2.14	MOE
4. Social Factor		
a. Social responsibilities	2.23	MOE
b. Mutual love / respect	2.28	MOE
c. Fidelity	2.12	MOE
d. Responsible parenthood	2.21	MOE
Total	28.78	
Average Weighted Mean	2.21	MOE

LEGEND:

MC	=	Much Contributed	2.34 – 3.00
MOC	=	Moderately Contributed	1.67 – 2.33
LC	=	Least Contributed	1.00 – 1.66
WM	=	Weighted Mean	
DE	=	Descriptive Equivalent	

C. Along emotional factors, the 3 items were perceived to have moderate effect. They were: personal discipline ($X=2.29$) self-worth / self-esteem ($X=2.14$) and integrity / honesty ($X=2.11$).

D. Along social factors, all the 4 items were perceived to have moderate effect on the personality of teachers. They were: mutual love / respect ($X=2.28$); social responsibilities ($X=2.23$), responsible parenthood ($X=2.21$) and fidelity ($X=2.12$).

The average weighted mean of 2.21 shows that the teachers perceived that the physical, intellectual, emotional and social factors have moderate effect on the personality of teachers.

The findings implied that teachers should strive to strengthen / enhance their intellectual abilities through intensive and consistent readings. They could become more creative and critical if they have a broad knowledge of their subject areas and other related areas since according to Lardizabal present – day teaching demands that a teachers possesses a general understanding of other branches of knowledge. If a teacher expects to help children understand and appreciate the world they live in, he must understand the interrelation and interdependence of the various areas of knowledge. He much be able to show his subject relates with other fields, particularly in the solution of life's problems.

Furthermore, at present have wide ranges of interest, background, experiences, and abilities. Even primary grade children talk with some degree of understanding about astronauts and space travel. A teacher, therefore must be ready to cope with possible questions relating to other fields be ready to cope with possible questions relating to other fields of knowledge children might raise. A broad general background is especially needed by the elementary school teacher of the self-contained classroom wherein he teaches the content of most subjects. Such a background must include the study of the arts, languages, philosophy, mathematics, literature, and physical sciences.

Table 2.3 presents the level of effect of the factors that affect the personality of teachers as perceived by the teachers of District IV.

Table 2.3

Level of Effects of the Factors that Affect the Personality of Teaches as Perceived by the Teachers

Factors	WM	DE
1. Physical Factor		
a. Physical fitness	2.27	MOE
b. Cleanliness	2.04	MOE
c. Beauty	2.07	MOE
d. Art	2.33	MOE
2. Intellectual Factors		
a. Knowledge / truth	2.21	MOE
b. Creative and critical thinking	2.31	MOE
3. Emotional Factor		
a. Integrity / honesty	2.01	MOE
b. Personal discipline	2.14	MOE
c. Self worth / self esteem	2.23	MOE
4. Social Factor		
a. Social responsibilities	2.14	MOE
b. Mutual love / respect	2.25	MOE
c. Fidelity	2.15	MOE
d. Responsible parenthood	2.13	MOE
Total	28.28	
Average Weighted Mean	2.18	MOE

LEGEND:

MC	=	Much Contributed	2.34 – 3.00
MOC	=	Moderately Contributed	1.67 – 2.33
LC	=	Least Contributed	1.00 – 1.66
WM	=	Weighted Mean	
DE	=	Descriptive Equivalent	

A. Along physical factors, the teachers of District IV perceived that all of the items had moderate effect on the personality of teachers. They were sequenced as follows: art ($X=2.33$) physical fitness ($X=2.27$); beauty ($X=2.07$) and cleanliness ($X=2.04$).

B. Along intellectual factors, both items were perceived to have moderate effect to personality. They were: creativity and critical thinking ($X=2.31$) and knowledge / truth ($X=2.21$).

C. Along emotional factors, all 3 items were perceived to have moderate effect. They were: self-worth/self-esteem ($X=2.23$); personal discipline ($X=2.14$) and integrity / honesty ($X=2.01$).

D. Along social factors, all 4 items were perceived to have moderate effect on personality. They were sequenced as follows: mutual love/respect ($X=2.25$); fidelity ($X=2.15$); social responsibility ($X=2.14$) and responsible parenthood ($X=2.13$).

The average weighted mean of 2.18 shows that the factors had moderate effect on the personality of teachers.

Table 2.4 presents the comparison of the perceived level of effects of the factors that affect the personality of teachers.

Table 2.4

**Comparison of the Perceived Level of Effects of the Factors that
Affect the Personality of Teachers**

Factors	WM	DE
1. Physical Factor		
a. Physical fitness	2.35	ME
b. Cleanliness	2.17	MOE
c. Beauty	2.17	MOE
d. Art	2.17	MOE
2. Intellectual Factors		
a. Knowledge / truth	2.32	MOE
b. Creative and critical thinking	2.38	ME
3. Emotional Factor		
a. Integrity / honesty	2.22	MOE
b. Personal discipline	2.25	MOE
c. Self worth / self esteem	2.18	MOE
4. Social Factor		
a. Social responsibilities	2.24	MOE
b. Mutual love / respect	2.28	MOE
c. Fidelity	2.14	MOE
d. Responsible parenthood	2.23	MOE
Average Weighted Mean	2.23	MOE

F = 1.4 FO.05 = 2.80 df = 3.16

LEGEND:

MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00

MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33

LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66

WM = Weighted Mean

DE = Descriptive Equivalent

A. Along physical factors, the four groups of respondents perceived that of 4 items, only 1 had much effect on personality while the 3 had moderate effect. They were sequenced as follows: physical fitness (X=2.35); cleanliness (X=2.17); art (X=2.17); and beauty (X=2.09).

B. Along intellectual factors, creativity and critical thinking had much effect (X=2.38) while knowledge / truth had moderate effect (X=2.32).

C. Along emotional factors, all 3 items were perceived to have moderate effect on personality. They were: personality discipline (X=2.25); integrity / honesty (X=2.22) and self-worth/self-esteem (X=2.18).

D. Along social factors, all items were perceived to have moderate effect. They were sequenced as follows: mutual love / respect (X=2.28); social responsibilities (X=2.24); responsible parenthood (X=2.18); and fidelity (X=2.14).

The average weighted mean of 2.23 shows that the 4 groups of teachers perceived that the physical, intellectual, emotional and social factors had moderate effect on the personality of teachers.

Moreover, the teachers of District I had the highest perceptions as shown by the average weighted mean of 2.28. This was followed with an average weighted mean of 2.24, with an average weighted mean of 2.21 with an average weighted mean of 2.18. In spite of the varied numeric, the descriptive equivalent all point to moderate effect.

In the hypothesis testing, the computed F-value of 0.429 was lower than the tabular F-value of 2.80 at 5 percent level of significance with 3.16. This means that there is no significant difference among the perceptions of the 4 groups of teachers. The null hypothesis that states: There is no significant difference among the perceptions of the teachers on the level of effect of the factors that affect the personality of teachers, is, therefore, accepted. It means that their perceptions were similar.

Degree of Seriousness of Problems Encountered by Teachers Relative to their Personality

The teacher perceived on the degree of seriousness of problems they encountered in regard their personality. The problems encountered were: poor physical appearance, lack of intellectual capacity, lack of self-control, impatient / unsympathetic, neglectful / noncaring, and full of pretenses / insecure / unfriendly.

Table 3

Degree of Seriousness of Problems Encountered by Teachers Relative to their Personality as Perceived by the Teachers in District I

Problems	WM	DE
1. Poor physical appearance	1.75	MS
2. Lack of intellectual capacity	1.82	MS
3. Lack of self-control / impatient / unsympathetic	1.85	MS
4. Neglectful / non – caring	1.78	MS
5. Full of pretenses / insincere / unfriendly	1.76	MS
Total	8.96	
Average Weighted Mean	1.79	MS

LEGEND:

MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00

MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33

LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66

WM = Weighted Mean

DE = Descriptive Equivalent

Table 3 presents the degree of seriousness of problems encountered by teachers relative to their personality as perceived by the teachers in District I.

The average weighted mean of 1.79 shows that the teachers encounter moderately serious problems.

On the 5 items, all were perceived to be moderately serious. They were ordered as follows: lack of self-control ($X=1.85$); lack of intellectual capacity ($X=1.82$); neglectful / uncaring ($X=1.78$); full of pretenses / insecure / unfriendly ($X=1.76$); and poor physical appearance ($X=1.75$).

The findings implied that the teachers should exercise more self-control. They should not explode momentarily for every slight misbehavior of the children.

Poor physical appearance was perceived least moderately serious. It means that the teachers have a positive attitude towards themselves and have accepted and appreciated what nature has given them. It is a sign of mature outlook.

Table 3.1 presents the degree of seriousness of problems encountered by teachers relative to their personality as perceived by the teachers.

The average weighted mean of 1.78 shows that the teachers encountered moderately serious problems in relation to their personality.

Table 3.1

Degree of Seriousness of Problems Encountered by Teachers Relative to their Personality as Perceived by the Teachers

Problems	WM	DE
1. Poor physical appearance	1.72	MS
2. Lack of intellectual capacity	1.81	MS
3. Lack of self-control / impatient / unsympathetic	1.87	MS
4. Neglectful / non – caring	1.73	MS
5. Full of pretenses / insincere / unfriendly	1.77	MS
Total	8.9	
Average Weighted Mean	1.78	MS

LEGEND:

MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00

MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33

LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66

WM = Weighted Mean

DE = Descriptive Equivalent

All of the items were perceived moderately serious. They were ordered as follows: lack of self-control ($X=1.87$); lack of intellectual capacity ($X=1.81$); full of pretenses / insecure / unfriendly ($X=1.77$); neglectful / noncaring ($X=1.73$); and poor physical appearance ($X=1.72$).

Table 3.2 presents the degree of seriousness of problems encountered by teachers in relation to their personality as perceived by the teachers in District III.

The average weighted mean of 1.81 shows that the teachers encountered moderately serious problems in relation to their personality.

All the items were perceived as moderately serious problems. They were ordered as follows: lack of intellectual capacity ($X=1.85$); impatient / unsympathetic ($X=1.84$); neglectful / noncaring ($X=1.80$); poor physical appearance ($X=1.79$); and, full of pretenses / insincere / unfriendly.

Table 3.2

Degree of Seriousness of Problems Encountered by Teachers Relative to their Personality as Perceived by the Teachers

Problems	WM	DE
1. Poor physical appearance	1.79	MS
2. Lack of intellectual capacity	1.85	MS
3. Lack of self-control / impatient / unsympathetic	1.84	MS
4. Neglectful / non – caring	1.80	MS
5. Full of pretenses / insincere / unfriendly	1.7	MS
Total	9.05	
Average Weighted Mean	1.81	MS

LEGEND:

MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00

MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33

LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66

WM = Weighted Mean

DE = Descriptive Equivalent

Table 3.2 further implies that the important and unsympathetic teacher emerges as second in the sequenced moderately serious problems.

Patience is a quality that a teacher must cultivate. A teacher must possess this in order to attain the educational objectives with the most desired results. He/She must be patient with the fast, average or slow learners. Fast learners require enrichment activities to challenge their intellectual abilities; to make learning meaningful to them. The teacher has to be patient to provide them these needs. The average learners have to be provided with varied activities. Likewise, the slow learners have to be treated with different activities to ease their difficulties, to motivate them to want to learn, hence, to raise them above their level.

Self-control is a matter of self-discipline that a teacher must impose on himself / herself in the midst of the teaching – learning situation. It is a quality that would make the teacher enjoy being with children of varied behavior / intellectual abilities. Liking children and understanding them is the key to self-control. If a teacher understand behavior and their causes, then he/she would not be child who may not be listening / participating; who fail to fulfill requirements; who teases classmates, etc.

The varied children's misbehavior observed daily from slight to serious are tests of the teacher's settle to cope with them cool-handed. The teacher has to conduct guidance and

counseling, instead of the traditional corporal punishment because the teacher often goes off the handle.

The teacher who is sympathetic is a skin to one who is understanding. He/She is sympathetic because he/she understands the child's situation / condition. For instance, a child is uneasy and manifests inattentiveness in class as a result of a skin disease. A teacher who is sympathetic would get into the root cause of the problem; tactfully confers with the parents for the child's medical treatment and so the problem is solved. The teacher then had helped to lift the pains/ discomfort of a suffering child. An adage runs: Sympathy is skin to love.

The next in the sequence of problems was the teacher who is full of pretenses / insincere and unfriendly.

This implies that the teacher should be sincere in his / her dealings with others in school and in the community. In school, the students can detect easily if the teacher, as an individual, is sincere in his job or not. It he/she devoted in this job? Is he devoted to student affairs?

In the community, the teacher should be sensitive to teacher is in community affairs and in his functions thereat. Even his personal dealings are judged since the community people can measure his actuations and whatever communications he engages in.

The findings implied that the teachers need to cultivate their inherit mental capacities.

Table 3.3 presents the degree of seriousness of problems encountered by teachers in Relative to their personality as perceived by the teachers in District IV.

The average weighted mean of 1.92 shows that the teachers encountered moderately serious problems.

All the items were perceived to be moderately serious. They were ordered as follows: full of pretenses / insecure / unfriendly ($X=2.16$); neglectful / noncaring ($X=1.98$); lack of self-control ($X=1.88$); lack of intellectual capacity ($X=1.83$); and poor physical appearance ($X=1.79$).

Table 3.3

Degree of Seriousness of Problems Encountered by Teachers Relative to their Personality as Perceived by the Teachers

Problems	WM	DE
1. Poor physical appearance	1.79	MS
2. Lack of intellectual capacity	1.83	MS
3. Lack of self-control / impatient / unsympathetic	1.88	MS
4. Neglectful / non – caring	1.93	MS
5. Full of pretenses / insincere / unfriendly	1.16	MS
Total	9.59	
Average Weighted Mean	1.92	MS

LEGEND:

MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00

MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33

LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66

WM = Weighted Mean

DE = Descriptive Equivalent

The findings implied that the teachers have to be assisted in regard self-acceptance, about what actually exists among themselves, accept that what exists can also be modified so that one can excel in his own unique way. Teachers are adults but they need assurances and reassurances until they gain their self-confidence. They have to be made to feel important. They have to be provided with activities / assignments in school whereby their unique capacities are cultivated. Such opportunities would make them feel that they can do something tangible truly well. Then, the other desirable traits will follow.

Moreover, the teachers do not believe that they have poor physical appearance. Each one is beautiful in his / her own way.

Table 3.4 presents the comparison of the perceived degree of seriousness of problems encountered by the teachers in relation to their personality.

The combined perceptions show that the teachers encountered moderately serious problems as proven by the average weighted mean of 1.82.

All the items were perceived to be moderately serious. The 4 groups of teachers sequenced the problems as follows: lack of self-control / impatient / unsympathetic ($X=1.86$);

full of pretenses / insincere / unfriendly ($X=1.85$); lack of intellectual capacity ($X=1.83$); neglectful / noncaring ($X=1.81$); and, poor physical appearance ($X=1.76$).

Table 3.4

Comparison of the Perceived Degree of Seriousness of Problems Encountered by the Teachers Relative to their Personality

Problems	WM	DE
1. Poor physical appearance	1.76	MS
2. Lack of intellectual capacity	1.83	MS
3. Lack of self-control / impatient / unsympathetic	1.86	MS
4. Neglectful / non – caring	1.81	MS
5. Full of pretenses / insincere / unfriendly	1.85	MS
Average Weighted Mean	1.82	MS

LEGEND:

MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00

MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33

LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66

WM = Weighted Mean

DE = Descriptive Equivalent

The findings implied that the four groups of respondents averred that they all have to be patient in order to achieve their educational goals. When one is patient he/she does not lose her temper easily. When one is patient, she is sympathetic to the learners. As Lardizabal states that the personal qualities of a teacher are related to their professional qualities. She specifies that a second essential of effective teaching is knowledge of children. This means understanding the basic principles of human growth and development. If a teacher expects to guide learning effectively, he must know how much children at various levels of maturity are capable of learning. He must know their interests and previous experiences which he can utilize in motivating them. He must know the adjustments children have to make at various stages of development and physical, emotional, and social problems they face in growing up. He must develop the special skills needed in gathering information about children.

It is not enough, however, for a teacher to know the characteristics of children. Equally important is he must like them. One can hardly be expected to stimulate children's growth if he does not find any satisfaction in working with them. Only a teacher who has genuine and sincere love for children can imbue them with love for learning.

In the testing, the F-computed value of 2.90 was lower than the F-tabular value at 5 percent level of significance with 3.16 degrees of freedom. It shows that there was no significant difference between the perceptions of the four groups of respondents and so the null hypothesis is accepted. It means that their perceptions were similar.

Degree of Need to Improve the Personality of Teachers

The teaches in the four districts in San Carlos City perceived on the degree of need to improve the personality of teachers. The needs for personality improvement are: 1) sharing one's problems with someone frequently results in new insights and understanding of the problem; 2) emulating traits which society evaluates as good; 3) improve one's social effectiveness; 4) considering one's problems alone to gain the best perspective; and 5) understanding one's personality; the better equipped to guide oneself and regulate one's life.

Table 4.0 presents the degree of need to improve the personality of teachers perceived that the improvement of the personality of teachers was moderately needed.

Table 4
Degree of Need to Improve the Personality of Teachers as
Perceived by the Teachers

Need to Improve Personality	WM	DE
1. Sharing one's problems with some one frequently results in new insights and understandings of the problem	2.27	MN
2. Emulating traits which society evaluates as good	2.12	MN
3. Working hard enough to improve one's social effectiveness	2.13	MN
4. Considering one's problems along to gain the best perspective	1.97	MN
5. Understanding one's personality; the better equipped to guide one-self and regulate one's life	1.87	MN
Total	10.36	
Average Weighted Mean	2.07	MON

LEGEND:

MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00

MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33

LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66

WM = Weighted Mean

DE = Descriptive Equivalent

All the items were perceived to be moderately needed. They were sequenced as follows: sharing one’s problems with someone results in new insights and understanding of the problem ($X=2.27$); improve one’s social effectiveness ($X=2.13$); emulating traits which society evaluates as good ($X=2.12$); considering one’s problems alone to gain the best perspective ($X=1.97$) and, understanding one’s personality, the better equipped to guide oneself and regulate one’s life.

Table 4.1 presents the degree of need to improve the personality of teachers as perceived by the teacher.

Table 4.1
Degree of Need to Improve the Personality of Teachers as
Perceived by the Teachers

Need to Improve Personality	WM	DE
1. Sharing one’s problems with some one frequently results in new insights and understandings of the problem	2.23	MON
2. Emulating traits which society evaluates as good	2.20	MON
3. Working hard enough to improve one’s social effectiveness	2.19	MON
4. Considering one’s problems along to gain the best perspective	1.77	MON
5. Understanding one’s personality; the better equipped to guide one-self and regulate one’s life	1.97	MON
Total	10.36	
Average Weighted Mean	2.07	MON

LEGEND:

- MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00
- MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33
- LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66
- WM = Weighted Mean
- DE = Descriptive Equivalent

The average weighted mean of 2.02 shows that there was a moderate need to improve the personality. They were sequenced as follows: sharing one’s problems with someone frequently results in new insights and understanding of the problems ($X=2.23$); emulating traits which society evaluates as good ($X=2.20$); improve one’s social effectiveness ($X=2.19$); understanding one’s personality; the better equipped to guide oneself and regulate one’s life: ($X=1.97$); and, considering one’s problems alone to gain the best perspective ($X=1.79$).

The findings implied that peer counseling among teachers is needed in order that they

could cope with their personality problems. A teacher needs another human being whom to confide with; a true friend who can tell what clothes fit you best; not to utter those words again; to admire your fate and not to curse it; that you are lucky to have been blessed with the best husband in the world after confiding that he is the worst person that came your way, etc.

Furthermore, the teachers perceived that a teacher can improve his/her personality if he/she lives within the norms of society.

Table 4.2 presents the degree of need to improve the personality of teachers as perceived by the teachers of District III.

The average weighted mean of 2.12 shows that there was a moderate need to improve the teacher's personality.

Table 4.2
Degree of Need to Improve the Personality of Teachers as
Perceived by the Teachers of District III

Need to Improve Personality	WM	DE
1. Sharing one's problems with some one frequently results in new insights and understandings of the problem	2.23	MON
2. Emulating traits which society evaluates as good	2.39	MN
3. Working hard enough to improve one's social effectiveness	2.15	MON
4. Considering one's problems along to gain the best perspective	1.99	MON
5. Understanding one's personality; the better equipped to guide one-self and regulate one's life	1.83	MON
Total	10.59	
Average Weighted Mean	2.12	MON

LEGEND:

MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00

MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33

LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66

WM = Weighted Mean

DE = Descriptive Equivalent

Four of the 5 items were perceived to be moderately needed. Only one was perceived as much needed. They were sequence as follows: emulating traits which uates as good ($X=2.39$); sharing one's problem with one frequently results in new insights and understanding ($X=2.23$); improve one's social effectiveness ($X=1.99$); and, understanding one's personality; the better to guide oneself and regulate one's life ($X=1.83$).

The findings implied that the teachers need the sanctions of society which control everyone's behavior. One's personality is good if one lives by the rules of the group he/she belongs. A teacher has to be accepted and acceptable because society judges him/her that way.

Oftentimes, teachers are assigned in other communities other than their own. There is a need therefore for these teachers to study the values of the society they are thrown in order to emulate what they evaluate as good.

The Code of Ethics contains that sort of relationship with the community that specifies as: 1) The teacher should actively participate as well as initiate community movements for moral, social, educational, economic and civic betterment. 2) as an intellectual leader, he should be willing to share his knowledge, training and experience with the community; and 3) He should conduct himself in the Code of Ethics for Filipino Teachers.

Table 4.3
Degree of Need to Improve the Personality of Teachers as
Perceived by the Teachers

Need to Improve Personality	WM	DE
1. Sharing one's problems with some one frequently results in new insights and understandings of the problem	2.21	MON
2. Emulating traits which society evaluates as good	2.32	MON
3. Working hard enough to improve one's social effectiveness	2.11	MON
4. Considering one's problems along to gain the best perspective	2.01	MON
5. Understanding one's personality; the better equipped to guide oneself and regulate one's life	1.79	MON
Total	10.44	
Average Weighted Mean	2.09	MON

LEGEND:

MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00

MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33

LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66

WM = Weighted Mean

DE = Descriptive Equivalent

Table 4.4 presents the comparison of the perceptions of the teachers on the degree of need to improve the personality of teachers.

The combined perceptions show that the teachers moderately need to improve their personality. This was shown by the average weighted mean of 2.09.

Table 4.4

Comparison of the Perceptions of the Teachers in Districts I, II, III and IV on the Degree of Need to Improve the Personality of Teachers

Need to Improve Personality	WM	DE
1. Sharing one's problems with some one frequently results in new insights and understandings of the problem	2.24	MON
2. Emulating traits which society evaluates as good	2.26	MON
3. Working hard enough to improve one's social effectiveness	2.15	MON
4. Considering one's problems along to gain the best perspective	2.94	MON
5. Understanding one's personality; the better equipped to guide one-self and regulate one's life	1.87	MON
Average Weighted Mean	2.09	MON

LEGEND:

MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00

MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33

LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66

WM = Weighted Mean

DE = Descriptive Equivalent

Taking the perceptions by groups, all of them perceived that there was a moderate need to improve their personality. This is shown by the following sequence.

In the hypothesis testing, the F-computed value of 0.175 was lower than the F-tabular value of 5 percent level of significance with 3.16 degrees of freedom. Thus the null hypothesis that states, "There are no significant difference among the perceptions of the teachers in the four districts of San Carlos City on the degree of need to improve their personality" is accepted.

Extent by which the Teachers Believe that Physical Characteristics Play a Part on the Impression The Make on Others

The teachers in the 4 district perceived on the extent by which they believe that physical characteristics play a part on the impression they make on others. These were: a person who cannot look at you in the eye when he speaks cannot be trusted; a good estimate of intelligence

can be made by studying a person's face; a high forehead is an evidence of high intelligence; people with close – set eyes cannot be trusted; certain lines on the palm / hands can be used to tell one's future.

The table 5.0 presents the extent which teachers in District I believe that physical characteristics play a part on the impression they make on others.

Table 5

Extent to which the Teachers Believe that Physical Characteristics Play a Part on the Impression they Make on Others

Physical Characteristics that Play a Part on Impression	WM	DE
1. A person who cannot look at you in the eye when he speaks cannot be trusted.	2.04	MOE
2. A good estimate of intelligence can be made by studying a person's face.	1.83	MOE
3. A high forehead is an evidence of high intelligence.	1.5	LE
4. People with close-set eyes cannot be trusted.	1.39	LE
5. Certain lines on the palm / hands can be used to tell one's future.	1.49	LE
Total	8.25	
Average Weighted Mean	1.65	LE

LEGEND:

MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00

MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33

LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66

WM = Weighted Mean

DE = Descriptive Equivalent

The average weighted mean of 1.65 shows that physical characteristics play the least extent on the impression they make on others.

Taking the items apart, 2 of them were perceived to have moderate extent. They were: a person who cannot look at you in the eye when he speaks cannot be trusted ($X=2.04$) and a good estimate of intelligence can be made by studying a person face ($X=1.83$). The rest were perceived to have least effect. They were: a high forehead is an evidence of high intelligence ($X=1.15$); certain lines on the palm / hands can be used to tell one's future ($X=1.49$) and people with close-set eyes cannot be trusted ($X=1.39$).

The findings implied that the teachers believe that the eyes being the mirror of one's soul do not deceive. They reflect what the person truly feels. If he is telling the truth, you can observe it in his eyes. That's the reason people who are conversing look at each other's eyes in order to determine the veracity of each other's ideas / opinions.

On the other hand, the teachers believe that the manner the eyes are situation has the least effect. It is because that had been genetically placed and that does not truly play a part on the judgment regarding a person's characteristics. The teachers do not judge a person through how nature has molded him physically.

Table 5.1 presents the extent by which the teachers in District II believe that physical characteristics play a part on the impression they make on others.

The average weighted mean of 2.05 shows that the teachers believe that physical characteristics have a moderate extent on the impression they make on others.

Table 5.1

Extent by which the Teachers Believe that Physical Characteristics Play a Part on the Impression they Make on Others

Physical Characteristics that Play a Part on Impression	WM	DE
1. A person who cannot look at you in the eye when he speaks cannot be trusted.	2.05	MOE
2. A good estimate of intelligence can be made by studying a person's face.	1.79	MOE
3. A high forehead is an evidence of high intelligence.	1.55	LE
4. People with close-set eyes cannot be trusted.	1.43	LE
5. Certain lines on the palm / hands can be used to tell one's future.	1.57	LE
Total	8.39	
Average Weighted Mean	1.68	LE

LEGEND:

MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00

MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33

LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66

WM = Weighted Mean

DE = Descriptive Equivalent

However, the 5 items were perceived differently. There were two that had moderate effect. They were: a person who cannot look at you in the eye when he speaks cannot be trusted ($X=2.05$) and a good estimate of intelligence can be made by studying a persons face ($X=1.79$). The items that were perceived to have least effect were: certain lines on the palm/hands can be used to tell one's future ($X=1.57$); a high forehead is an evidence of high intelligence ($X=1.55$); and; people with close set eyes cannot be trusted ($X=1.43$).

The findings implied that the teachers do not consider inborn characteristics such as closed – set eyes or a high forehead as tangible reasons to judge a person's personality. They believe that it is the inner person himself that determines what the person truly is. It is more on how the person was reared and how he himself used his will and intellect to shape his personality. The teachers are very much aware that “the action of the body is nothing but the act of the will objectified... it is only in reflection that the will and to act are different”. What we know of ourselves within our consciousness is that “we are not merely a knowing subject, but, in another aspect, we ourselves also belong to the inner nature that is to be known. We ourselves are the thing in itself. And the thing in itself is will, the act of will is the closest and most distinct manifestation of the thing in itself. This, then, is that single narrow door to truth, namely, the discovery that the will is the essence of each person.

The foregoing philosophical statements explain why the teachers in District II believe that physical characteristics such as forehead, set of eyes, lines on hands, etc. do not determine the personality of a person but it is the inner person that is being manifested in his words and deeds.

Table 5.2 presents the extent by which the teachers in district III believe that physical characteristics play a part on the impression they make on others.

Table 5.2

Extent by which the Teachers Believe that Physical Characteristics Play a Part on the Impression they Make on Others

Physical Characteristics that Play a Part on Impression	WM	DE
1. A person who cannot look at you in the eye when he speaks cannot be trusted.	2.03	MOE
2. A good estimate of intelligence can be made by studying a person's face.	1.87	MOE
3. A high forehead is an evidence of high intelligence.	1.47	LE
4. People with close-set eyes cannot be trusted.	1.43	LE
5. Certain lines on the palm / hands can be used to tell one's future.	1.48	LE
Total	8.28	
Average Weighted Mean	1.66	LE

LEGEND:

MC	=	Much Contributed	2.34 – 3.00
MOC	=	Moderately Contributed	1.67 – 2.33
LC	=	Least Contributed	1.00 – 1.66
WM	=	Weighted Mean	
DE	=	Descriptive Equivalent	

The teachers believe that physical characteristics play the least extent on the impression they make on others. This is shown by the average weighted mean of 1.66.

Of the 5 items, two were perceived to play a moderate extent on the impression they make on others. They were: a person who cannot look at you in the eye when he speaks cannot be trusted ($X=2.03$); and, a good estimate of intelligence can be made by studying a person's face ($X=1.87$).

Those that were perceived to play a moderate extent on the expression they make on others were: certain lines on the palm/hands can be used to tell one's future ($X=1.48$); a high forehead is an evidence of high intelligence ($X=1.47$); and people with close-set eyes cannot be trusted ($X=1.43$).

The findings implied that the teachers believed that studying a man's face is a technique in determining a person's intelligence. It is because the face serves as the mask of a person but it is more than that. A person's facial expressions depict his reactions to certain situations, certain ideas, problems, issues etc. Even without the person speaking observe a his face, how intelligently he is reacting. How his eyes light up, how he purses his lips, how his face color flashes/blushes/pales at certain situations. These and other instances make us believe that the teacher-respondents were very observant on human nature.

Table 5.3 presents the extent by which the teachers in District IV believe that physical characteristics play a part on the impression they make on others.

The teachers believe that the physical characteristics play a moderate extent on the impression they make on others. This was evidenced by the average weighted mean of 1.92.

Table 5.3

Extent by which the Teachers in District IV Believe that Physical Characteristics Play a Part on the Impression they

Make on Others

Physical Characteristics that Play a Part on Impression	WM	DE
1. A person who cannot look at you in the eye when he speaks cannot be trusted.	1.64	LE
2. A good estimate of intelligence can be made by studying a person's face.	1.9	LE
3. A high forehead is an evidence of high intelligence.	1.98	MOE
4. People with close-set eyes cannot be trusted.	2.11	MOE
5. Certain lines on the palm / hands can be used to tell one's future.	1.99	MOE
Total	9.62	
Average Weighted Mean	1.92	MOE

LEGEND:

MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00

MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33

LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66

WM = Weighted Mean

DE = Descriptive Equivalent

Of the 5 items, 4 were perceived to play a moderate extent. While only one played the least extent. They were sequenced as follows: people with close-set eyes cannot be trusted ($X=2.11$); a high forehead is an evidence of high intelligence ($X=1.98$); certain lines on the palm/hands can be used to tell one's future ($X=1.99$); and, a good estimate of intelligence can be made by studying a person's face ($X=1.9$). A person who cannot look at you in the eye when he speaks cannot be trusted played the least extent ($X=1.64$) on the impression they make on others.

The findings imply that the teachers in District IV believe moderately on the extent that physical characteristics play on the impression they make on others. They believe that what nature has bestowed on a person determines a component of his personality and that by seeing the individual physically you can judge instantly his personality. They are permanent marks that tell the world what kind of person he is. This is the instance whereby people who read personality those physical aspects will either love or hate someone at first sight because he has a

predetermined criteria about the person – just by looking at the person physically. In other words they are fatalists who believe that a person is born with the kind of personality; that it is his nature; that the personality of a person is due to the inborn marks in him, that determine his behavior.

Table 5.4 presents the comparison of the perceptions of the teachers on the extent by which they believe that physical characteristics play a part on the impression they make on others.

The combined perceptions of the 4 groups of respondents show that they believe that the physical characteristics play a moderate extent on the impression they make on others. This was proven by the average weighted mean of 1.73.

Table 5.4

Comparison of the Perceived Extent by which Teachers Believe that Physical Characteristics Play a Part on the Impression they make on Others

Physical Characteristics that Play a Part on Impression	WM	DE
1. A person who cannot look at you in the eye when he speaks cannot be trusted.	1.94	MOE
2. A good estimate of intelligence can be made by studying a person's face.	1.85	MOE
3. A high forehead is an evidence of high intelligence.	1.63	LE
4. People with close-set eyes cannot be trusted.	1.59	LE
5. Certain lines on the palm / hands can be used to tell one's future.	1.63	LE
Average Weighted Mean	1.73	MOE

LEGEND:

MC = Much Contributed 2.34 – 3.00

MOC = Moderately Contributed 1.67 – 2.33

LC = Least Contributed 1.00 – 1.66

WM = Weighted Mean

DE = Descriptive Equivalent

Taking the four groups of respondents alongside each other, perceived the highest with an average weighted mean of 1.92 or moderate extent. This was followed by District with an average weighted mean of 1.68 or moderate extent ($X=1.66$) or least extent and ($X=1.65$) or least extent. In the testing, the F-computed value of 1.5 was higher than the F-tabular value of 3.24 at 5 percent level of significance with 3/16 degree of freedom. It means that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the 4 groups of teachers. Therefore the null hypothesis that states: There are no significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers in four district of San Carlos City on the extent by which the teachers believe that physical characteristics play a part on the impression they make on others, is, therefore accepted, means that their perceptions are similar.

The findings implied that the teachers agree that physical characteristics play to a moderate extent on the impressions they make on others. They believe what Kupunan states as a means of prediction whereby lives of one's hand tell the fate and destiny of an individual. It is also believed that the form and shape of one's had reveal personality traits.

Still another technique of character analysis is phrenology, whereby an individual's traits such as honesty, sympathy, love, mathematical ability, or musical talent can be determined by the size and shape of the head, the form of the forehead, and so on.

On the foregoing beliefs, the teachers moderately agree and there is no significant difference among their perceptions.

Lardizabal states that the personal qualities of an effective teacher are so interrelated with professional qualities that it is hard to isolate them. Besides personal qualities are intangible and, therefore, difficult to measure.

Various studies, mostly on students' opinions, have been made to identify the personal qualities of an effective teacher. It is generally believed that students are the best judges regarding personal characteristics of teachers. These personal qualities are related to the five aspects of personality: intellectual, social, physical, emotional and moral. Among those rated highly are the following:

1. Pleasing, personal appearance, manner, courtesy, pleasant voice
2. Intelligence, emotional stability, and self control
3. Sympathy, kindness, helpfulness, patience
4. Integrity, trustworthiness, honesty, loyalty
5. Flexibility, creativity, resourcefulness
6. Sociability, friendliness, cooperativeness
7. Fairness, impartiality, Tolerance
8. Sense of humor, cheerfulness, enthusiasm

Knowledge and Truth

This determinate view of nature is further supported by Leibniz's theory of knowledge. A person, for example, is for Leibniz similar to a subject in the grammatical sense. For any true sentence or opposition, the predicate is already contained in the subject. Thus, to know the subject is already to know certain predicates. "All men are mortal" is a true proposition because the predicate mortal is already contained in the notion of men. Leibniz therefore says that in any true proposition, "I find that every predicate, necessary or contingent, past, present, or future, is comprised in the notion of the subject. Similarly, in the nature of things, all substances are, so to speak, subjects and the things they do are their predicates. Just as grammatical subjects contain their predicates, also existing substance already contain their future behavior.

Chapter 4

Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the summary of findings, draws the corresponding conclusions and forwards recommendations based on the results of the study on the following particular questions:

1. What is the level of contribution of personality traits of teachers to a wholesome personality?
 - 1.a Are there significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers in four public elementary school districts of San Carlos city on the level of contribution of personality traits of teachers to a wholesome personality?
2. What is the level of effects of the factors that affect the personality of teachers?
 - 2.a Are there significant differences among the perceptions of teachers in four public elementary school district of San Carlos City on the level of effect of the factors that affect the personality of teachers?
3. What is the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered by teachers relative to their personality?
 - 3.a Are there significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers in four public elementary school districts on the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered by the teachers relative to their personality?
4. What is the degree of need to improve the personality of teachers in four public elementary school?
 - 4.a. Are there significant difference among the perceptions of the teachers in four public elementary school on the degree of need to improve their personality?
5. To what extent do the teachers believe that physical characteristics play a part on the impressions they make on others?
 - 5.a Are there significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers on the extent by which the teachers believe that physical characteristics play a part on the impression they make on others?

The following null hypotheses were tested in this study:

1. There are significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers in public elementary school districts on the level of contribution of personality traits of teachers to a wholesome personality.
2. There is no significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers in 4 public elementary school on the level of effect of the factors that affect the personality of teachers.
3. There is no significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers in 4 public elementary school districts on the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered by the

teachers relative to their personality.

4. There is no significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers in 4 public elementary school on the degree of need to improve their personality.
5. There is no significant differences among the perceptions of the teachers in 4 public elementary school on the extent by which the teaches believe that physical characteristics play a part on the impressions they make on others.

Summary of Findings

The following are the salient findings of this study:

Level of Contribution of the Personality Traits of Teachers to Wholesome Personality

1. The teachers in 4 public elementary school districts of San Carlos City perceived that the personality traits of teachers had a moderate contribute to wholesome personality as shown by the average weighted mean of 2.15.
 - 1.a There was no significant difference among the perceptions of the teachers in 4 public elementary school as shown by the computed F-value of 0.12 which was lower than the F-tabular value of 2.95 at 5 percent level of significance with 3/28 degrees of freedom.

Level of Effect of the Factors that Affect the Personality of Teachers

2. The teachers in 4 public elementary school districts perceived that the factors had a moderate effect of the factors that affect personality of teachers as shown by their combined perceptions with an average weighted mean of 2.23.
 - 2.a. There was no significant differences among the perceptions of the 4 groups of respondents as shown by the F-computed value of 0.429 which was lower than the F-tabular value of 2.80 at 5 percent level of significance with 3/16 degrees of freedom.

Degree of Seriousness of Problems Encountered by the Teachers Relative to their Personality

3. The four groups of teachers encountered moderately serious problems relative to their personality as shown by the combined perceptions of 1.82.
 - 3.a There was no significant differences among the perceptions of the 4 groups of teachers as shown by the F-computed value of 2.90 which was lower than the F-tabular value of 3.24 at 5 percent level of significance with 3/16 degrees of freedom.

Degree of Need to Improve the Personality of Teachers

4. The 4 groups of teachers perceived that there was a moderate need to improve the personality of teachers as shown by their combined perceptions with an average weighted mean of 2.09.
 - 4.a. There was no significance among the perceptions of the 4 groups of teachers as shown by the F-computed value of 0.175 which was lower than the F-tabular value of 3.24 at 5

percent level of significance with 3/16 degrees of freedom.

Extent by which the Teachers Believe that Physical Characteristics Play a Part on the Impression They Make on Others

5. The 4 groups of teachers believed that physical characteristics play a moderate extent on the impression they make on others as shown by the combined perceptions with an average weighted mean of 1.73.
 - 5.a There was no significant difference among the perceptions of the 4 groups of teachers as shown by the F-computed value of 1.5 which was lower than the F-tabular value of 3.24 at 5 percent level of significance with 3/16 degrees of freedom.

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Personality traits of teachers moderately contributed to their wholesome personality.
 - 1.a The null hypothesis was accepted.
2. The factors moderately affect the personality of teachers.
 - 2.a The null hypothesis was accepted.
3. the teachers encountered moderately serious problems.
 - 3.a The null hypothesis was accepted.
4. There was a moderate need to improve the personality of teachers.
 - 4.a The null hypothesis was accepted.
5. Physical characteristics play a moderate extent on the impression they make on others.
 - 5.a The null hypothesis was accepted.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are forwarded:

1. The teachers of the 4 districts of San Carlos City should further strengthen their personality traits for a more wholesome personality.
2. The teachers of the 4 district of San Carlos City should seriously consider the social, emotional, intellectual and physical factors that affect their personality through introspection.
3. The teachers should be involved in intensive values education.
4. The teachers of the 4 districts of San Carlos City should adopt the identified needs to improve their personality.
5. The teachers should fully understand that some of the physical characteristics whereby individuals are characteristically judged do not have scientific basis

REFERENCES

A. Books

- Aquino, Gaudencio. *Fundamentals of Effective Teaching* Manila: Philippine Navotas Press, 2024.
- Castro, Victoria, et.al., *Integration as Practiced in the Philippines Normal College*, Manila: Manila Publishing House, 2022.
- Downie, N. M. and Health, R. W. *Basic Statistical Methods* New York: Harper and Row, Publishers Inc., 2024.
- Gregorio, Herman C. *Schools Administration and Supervision* Quezon City: Rex Book Store. 2019.
- Philosophy of Education in the Philippine Setting*, Quezon City: R. P. Garcia, 2019.
- Kapunan, Rocio Reyes. *Fundamentals of Guidance and Counseling*. Quezon City: R. P. Garcia, 2019.
- Kelly, James. *The Successful Teacher*. Metro Manila: The Athenians Press Inc., 2018.
- Klausmeier, Herbert J. et. Al. *Learning Human Abilities in Human Psychology*. New York: Harper and Row Publishing House. 2021.
- Kolesnik, Walter B. *Educational Psychology*. New York: MacGraw Hill Co., 2023.
- Strang, Ruth and Morris, Glyn. *Guidance in the Classroom*. New York: MacMillan Company. 2017.

B. Magazine

- Divina, Remedios. "The Role of Teachers in Education" *The Modern Teacher*. Manila: Paper Publishing Association of the Philippines, Inc., 2016.
- Lardizabal, Amparo S. "The New Teaching Effectiveness" *The Modern Teacher*. Manila: Publisher's Association of the Philippines, 2016.
- Powell, Douglas. "Correlates of Present Teacher Communication Frequency and Diversity", *Journal of Education*.2021.

C. Unpublished Materials

- Oducando, Yolanda O. "Personality Patterns of Elementary and High School Teachers in Relation to Efficiency Ratings" Unpublished Master's Thesis, de la Salle University, Manila, 2018.
- Sarrabia, Porfirio F. "Personality Traits and Characteristics of Elementary Grades Teachers in the Division of Pagadian City and Zambaonga del Sur, 2018-2019. Unpublished Master's Thesis, Misamis University, Ozamis City, 2020.